

Partition of Multinomial Coefficient

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Abstract: This paper focuses on the successive partition method applied to a multinomial coefficient like partition of a binomial coefficient in combinatorial geometric series. The coefficient for each term in combinatorial geometric series refers to a binomial coefficient. These ideas can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real life problems.

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1. Introduction

When the author of this article was trying to develop the multiple summations of geometric series, a new idea was stimulated his mind to create a combinatorial geometric series [1-13]. The combinatorial geometric series is a geometric series whose coefficient of each term of the geometric series denotes the binomial coefficient V_n^r . In this article, binomial identities and multinomial theorem is provided using the binomial coefficients for combinatorial geometric series.

2. Combinatorial Geometric Series

The combinatorial geometric series [1-13] is derived from the multiple summations of geometric series. The coefficient of each term in the combinatorial refers to the binomial coefficient V_n^r .

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \dots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i \quad \& \quad V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3) \dots (n+r-1)(n+r)}{r!},$$

where $n \geq 0, r \geq 1$ and $n, r \in N = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$.

Here, $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i$ refers to the combinatorial geometric series and

V_n^r is the binomial coefficient for combinatorial geometric series.

Theorem 2.1: $V_n^r = \frac{(n+r)!}{n! r!}$ where $n, r \geq 0$ & $n, r \in N$.

Proof. $\binom{n+r}{n} = \frac{(n+r)!}{n!(n+r-n)!} = \frac{(n+r)!}{n! r!} = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3) \dots (n+r)}{r!}$.

Here, $V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3) \dots (n+r)}{r!} = \prod_{i=1}^r \frac{n+i}{r!}$.

From the above expressions, we conclude that

$$V_n^r = \frac{(n+r)!}{n!r!}, \text{ where } n, r \geq 0 \text{ \& } n, r \in N.$$

Hence, theorem is proved.

3. Partition of Binomial Coefficient

Theorem 3.1: $V_n^r = V_n^{r-1} + V_r^{n-1}$, ($n, r \geq 1$ & $n, r \in N$).

Proof. Let us apply Theorem 2.1 in the partition of a binomial coefficient.

$$V_n^{r-1} + V_r^{n-1} = \frac{(n+r-1)!}{n!(r-1)!} + \frac{(r+n-1)!}{r!(n-1)!}, \quad \text{where } (n+r-1) = (r+n-1).$$

$$\text{So, } V_n^{r-1} + V_r^{n-1} = (n+r-1)! \left(\frac{1}{n!(r-1)!} + \frac{1}{r!(n-1)!} \right).$$

By simplifying this expression, we get

$$V_n^{r-1} + V_r^{n-1} = (n+r-1)! \left(\frac{r}{n!r!} + \frac{n}{r!n!} \right) = \frac{(n+r-1)!(r+n)}{n!r!} = \frac{(n+r)!}{n!r!} = V_n^r.$$

Hence, theorem is proved.

The successive partitions applied to a binomial coefficient (root) V_n^r are given below:

$$V_n^r = V_n^{r-1} + V_r^{n-1}.$$

$$V_n^r = (V_n^{r-2} + V_{r-1}^{n-1}) + (V_r^{n-2} + V_{n-1}^{r-1}).$$

$$V_n^r = (V_n^{r-3} + V_{r-2}^{n-1}) + (V_{r-1}^{n-2} + V_{n-1}^{r-2}) + (V_r^{n-3} + V_{n-2}^{r-1}) + (V_{n-1}^{r-2} + V_{r-1}^{n-2}).$$

Similarly, we can partition each item into sum of two parts again and again.

The final binomial coefficient (leaf) under the successive partitions of V_n^r (root) is given below:

$$V_{r-k}^{n-k} \text{ or } V_{n-k}^{r-k}, (n-k \geq 1 \text{ \& } r-k \geq 1).$$

The binomial coefficients between root and leaves are named as predecessors and successors.

Also, we can show these root, predecessors, successors, and leaves in a tree diagram.

4. Partition of Multinomial Coefficient

Theorem 4.1: $V_{p+q}^{m+n} = V_{p+q}^{m+n-1} + V_{m+n}^{p+q-1}$, ($m, n, p, q \geq 1$ & $m, n, p, q \in N$).

Proof. Let us prove this theorem like the Theorem 3.1.

$$\begin{aligned} V_{p+q}^{m+n-1} + V_{m+n}^{p+q-1} &= \left(\frac{(p+q+m+n-1)!}{(p+q)!(m+n-1)!} + \frac{(m+n+p+q-1)!}{(m+n)!(p+q-1)!} \right) \\ &= (m+n+p+q-1)! \left(\frac{1}{(p+q)!(m+n-1)!} + \frac{1}{(m+n)!(p+q-1)!} \right) \\ &= (m+n+p+q-1)! \left(\frac{(m+n)}{(p+q)!(m+n)!} + \frac{(p+q)}{(m+n)!(p+q)!} \right) \\ &= (m+n+p+q-1)! \left(\frac{(m+n+p+q)}{(p+q)!(m+n)!} \right) = \frac{(m+n+p+q)}{(m+n)!(p+q)!} = V_{p+q}^{m+n}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, theorem is proved.

$$\text{Note that } \frac{(m+n+p+q)!}{m!n!p!q!} = V_{p+q}^{m+n} \times V_n^m \times V_q^p.$$

Corollary 4.1: $V_{n_1+n_2+n_3+\dots+n_t}^{m_1+m_2+m_3+\dots+m_s} = V_{n_1+n_2+n_3+\dots+n_t}^{m_1+m_2+m_3+\dots+m_s-1} + V_{m_1+m_2+m_3+\dots+m_s}^{n_1+n_2+n_3+\dots+n_t-1}$.

5. Conclusion

In this article, partition of a multinomial coefficient has been introduced and this idea can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real life problems.

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